

Media between the Hammer of Promoting Extremism & the Anvil of Treatment

الإعلام بين مطرقة الترويج للتطرف وسندان المعالجة

Dr. Nabila Abdel Fattah keshty

PhD in constitutional law and political systems

Member of the International Union of Arab Academics

Noby.keshty2000@gmail.com

Abstract:

There is hardly any society that the people do not talk about extremism, its reasons and ways to overcome, as a result of its spread and penetration into Arab or foreign societies, and its increasing danger on both individuals as well as society.

There has been a huge argumentation that media plays a role to increase the numbers of extremists and those who have joined the terrorist groups.

Media has also been charged with a huge responsibility in decorating extremism for the ordinary people as it helps spreading crime in a negative dark way as well as exaggerating in the description of extremism as if it looks up to those who commit extremist actions that in turn destabilize the confidence in the society values and belief so we are trying through this treatise to stabilize the role of media effect on increasing extremism in society in the light of media terms.

The research problem lies in answering a major question: Did the media promote extremism or was it a tool for rejecting violence and extremism? The importance of the research is due to monitoring the reality of the media in order to work on finding solutions to reduce the phenomenon of extremism. The research aims to identify the strategies used to combat the phenomenon of extremism, in addition to evaluating the media's role in dealing with the phenomenon of extremism.

In their research paper, the researcher relied on the descriptive analytical approach by addressing the conceptual framework of extremism and analyzing the changing relationship between it and the media.

So that the reader can be put in the picture through which the media has tried to deal with extremism.

Keywords: extremism; media; treatment; terrorism; society.

الملخص:

لا يكاد يخلو مجتمع لا يتحدث فيه الناس عن التطرف وأسبابه وطرق معالجته، نظرًا لانتشاره وتغلغله في المجتمعات عربية كانت أم أجنبية، وازدياد خطورته على الفرد والمجتمع، وقد حدث جدال كبير حول دور وسائل الإعلام في العمل على زيادة عدد المتطرفين والملتحقين بصوف الإرهاب، وحملوها مسؤولية كبرى في تزيين التطرف في نفوس الناس، حيث تبالغ في وصف التطرف، وكأنها ترفع من شأن المتطرفين، مما يزعزع الثقة بقيم وعقيدة المجتمع.

وتكمن مشكلة البحث في الإجابة على تساؤل رئيس وهو هل روج الإعلام للتطرف أم كان أداة لنبذ العنف والتطرف؟ وترجع أهمية البحث إلى رصد واقع الإعلام للعمل على إيجاد حلول للحد من ظاهرة التطرف، ويهدف البحث إلى التعرف على الاستراتيجيات المستخدمة لمكافحة ظاهرة التطرف بالإضافة إلى تقييم الدور الإعلامي في تناول ظاهرة التطرف.

واعتمدت الباحثة في ورقتهما البحثية على المنهج الوصفي التحليلي من خلال التطرق للإطار المفاهيمي للتطرف وتحليل العلاقة المتغيرة بينه وبين الإعلام.

لذا سنحاول من خلال هذه الورقة البحثية أن نضع القارئ في الصورة التي يعالج من خلالها الإعلام التطرف.

الكلمات المفتاحية: التطرف؛ الإعلام؛ المعالجة؛ الإرهاب؛ المجتمع.

Introduction:

The topic of extremism has been covered by many studies from its various aspects. However, our treatment today will be from the angle of his relationship with the media (Styliqnou, 2003, p38), both, where the media plays a pivotal role in shaping public awareness of the need to confront the phenomenon of extremism and address its repercussions (Shaaban, 2006, p.13), But at the same time, it may constitute a strategic weapon for extremism, because it provides it with propaganda and promotion by spreading and broadcasting the words and actions of extremists (Al-Da'ja, 2008, p.4).

Research Problem:

The research problem crystallizes in answering the question (cause and effect) between media coverage and extremism, and did the media promote extremism? Has the media, through what it presents, had an impact in spreading the culture of extremism among segments of society? In order to answer these questions, this topic was chosen.

Research Importance:

The importance of the research lies in the following:

- 1- Monitoring the reality of the media as a first step to working to find solutions to reduce the phenomenon of extremism.
- 2- Explaining the causes, types and manifestations of extremism
- 3- Employing new mechanisms to combat the phenomenon of extremism.

Research Aims:

Determining the research objectives is one of the basic steps in order to reach integrated and correct results, so this research seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- 1- Explaining the reality of extremism and its dangers to society.
- 2- Identify the strategies used to combat the phenomenon of extremism.
- 3- Evaluating the media's role in addressing the phenomenon of extremism.
- 4- Providing a set of proposals to activate the role of the media in combating the phenomenon of extremism.

Research Methodology:

To achieve the aforementioned research objectives - and given the nature of the topic - the researcher relied on the descriptive and analytical approach, by addressing the conceptual framework of extremism and analyzing the changing relationship between it and the media.

Search Plan:

The researcher divides this research paper into two sections, then ends it with a conclusion and recommendations, as follows:

- The first topic: The role of the media in promoting extremism.
- The second topic: The role of the media in combating extremism.
- Conclusion.

The first topic: The role of media in promoting extremism

The media plays an important and influential role in the trends and directions of public opinion, and in formulating its positions and behaviors through the news and information provided to it by various media outlets. A person cannot form a specific position or adopt a specific idea except through the information and data that is provided to him, which confirms the ability of Media in all its forms and manifestations helps bring about changes in individual and societal concepts and practices. By spreading knowledge, awareness and enlightenment (Sharadha, 2016, p. 6), In addition to this positive role of the media, there is a negative role played by the media in developing the idea of extremism, which can be limited to helping in sowing violence and developing extremist ideology, directly or indirectly, in the following:

First: the space of absolute freedom

The space of freedom that the International Information Network (the Internet) granted to the adherents of these ideas in disseminating and promoting them, and providing the opportunity to publish their statements, statements, books, films, and recordings throughout the world with unprecedented ease and comfort (Musa, 2008, p.25), as global societies are connected to each other by technical information systems via satellites and international communication networks, the criminal danger of terrorist groups and organizations has increased, as they have invested their energy in

taking advantage of that technology and exploiting it to spread their extremist ideas (Al-Ajlan, 2008, p.5).

Every terrorist group or organization has many electronic brigades that adopt several means to destroy and destabilize societies, including distorting facts, glorifying traitors, and promoting enemy plans. This requires warning public opinion against being swayed by what is broadcast by these satanic brigades that control most social media outlets, and broadcast clips. Visual, audio, and short sentences and distribute them to millions of participants in a few minutes.

Second: Following a policy of intimidation and inflation

Some media outlets follow a policy of exaggeration and exaggeration to achieve journalistic excitement and public interest, for the purpose of financial profit in light of fierce competition (Al-Ani, 2013, p.44).

Third: false freedom

The news, pictures and articles broadcast by some newspapers and media outlets promote this thought, even indirectly, under the guise of false freedom (Badran, No. 373, 2014).

Fourth: The dominance of the news nature in media coverage

The absence of coverage of an analytical and interpretive nature leads to the media treatment remaining on the surface of the event or phenomenon. Which weakens her ability to persuade and makes her lose effective and tangible influence (Pickard, 2000, p.25).

Fifth: Lack of experts and specialists

Some media outlets lack experts and specialists in the security, social, psychological and educational fields. To convince the viewer of the reality of extremism, and not to be led by media exaggeration, which most often leads to counterproductive results.

The focus must also be on the therapeutic issue of the phenomenon of extremism, and the need to provide insights that help the reader or viewer to form a correct opinion (Abdel Fattah, 2014, p.23).

Sixth: The emergence of extremist thinkers through the media

Some satellite channels host those with extremist ideology and give them the opportunity to express their extremist opinions, as well as allowing them to create their own satellite channels where they can be allowed to present extremist ideology (Abdel Hamid, 2002, p.75).

I am referring here to a specific incident that caused controversy in Egypt, which was conducting a television dialogue with one of the terrorists who participated in a huge terrorist operation in the oasis region some time ago and who was later arrested. Media professionals were divided over the idea of the dialogue itself, some of whom objected because the dialogue gave the terrorist a media outlet to spread his idea. Extremist, and the supporters focused on the need to expose terrorists in front of

society so that it realizes the extent of the deviant and extremist ideology they adopt, which is a false ideology that has nothing to do with Islam.

Some believe that extensive publication about terrorism may lead to more terrorism, because terrorist groups and their actual and potential supporters are thirsty for such publication, and they may believe that extensive publication about terrorist operations will terrorize societies, but the danger is that these extremist groups seek to exploit the media's hunger to spread their news and ideas. And its terrorist operations, doubling those operations in a way that increases the number of victims - dead and injured - and achieves their goal of violence.

The media scoop claimed by some media outlets - especially foreign ones - is extremely harmful, especially since some of these media outlets are not subject to the professional and ethical standards of the society in which they operate. But it only cares about pleasing the countries from which it starts. In the terrorist incident that took place in the Egyptian oasis region, an international news agency and a famous American news channel competed in publishing false numbers about the number of victims of that operation among the Egyptian officers, which gave the terrorist leaders the opportunity to brag about their diabolical operation and broadcast. The spirit of defeat among the Egyptians and showing that the terrorists have control over the Egyptian police and army.

The international media made a mistake in this case because it is the natural resource for the electronic brigades of terrorist organizations and the rest of the tendentious social networking sites, and that is why we say here that this media treatment of the event is completely wrong, and harms society and undermines its resolve and morale, in exchange for raising the morale of terrorists and their inhumane supporters.

The second topic: The role of the media in combating extremism

In this era, the Arab media is witnessing a dynamic movement that is not limited to the official government media. Rather, there is the private media that has become a distinct presence alongside the government media, and this private media will support the official government media in confronting the phenomenon of extremism.

With the increase and intensity of terrorist operations that many Arab cities are exposed to, some people say that security and military confrontation is the only effective means of eliminating the phenomenon of terrorism and extremist groups that spread takfiri ideas and violence and tempt young people to join them through all means of temptation, whether worldly or as fairy tales. Heaven, and these people forget that the media has an effective role in combating extremist ideology (Ahmed, 2009, p.6).

The media is currently considered one of the most important weapons in managing intellectual issues and confronting extremism. The media may be the only means of mobilizing public opinion in any country towards a specific issue, so that it becomes an opinion that is either supportive of what this country is proposing and opposed to its enemies, or vice versa. Therefore, the media has a major function in This is the case and it must be revealing the reality and illuminating the public, meaning it should be a rational media to build a stable society, a media that avoids provocation, spreading discord and incitement against the state, a media that resists rumors on

social media sites that are controlled by extremists in the form of hypocritical groups that show the opposite of what they hide, with the aim of making them believe them. The unaware audience (Mustafa, 2015, p.132).

These suspicious sites do not hesitate to achieve their goal and their endeavors to destroy countries, and from here the media, with its loyal children, has the responsibility of making public opinion aware of the issues of its homeland so that it becomes a strong opinion against extremist ideology that can confront the plans of its owners.

Media professionals themselves must adopt effective mechanisms to win the fight against extremism, and that is why we say that objective media or rational media is the only mechanism to fortify public opinion against the electronic brigades that adopt counter-media that incites people against their leaders.

Then the successful media is the one that arranges its priorities at every stage, and at the present time we consider that confronting extremism is the main issue in Arab societies, and therefore the media participates strongly in confronting violence and extremism, and the media must be devoted, and all its capabilities must be harnessed in confronting this accursed scourge that strikes the future. Peoples, but without the media slipping into publishing what satisfies the terrorists' arrogance and thirst for bloodshed.

We are faced with a real dilemma if we address the role of the media in confronting operations of violence, extremism and terrorism. What is required is that the media does not harness its tools to promote the ideology of terrorist organizations and recruit those who sympathize with their ideas. Rather, what is required is to focus on the enlightening role of the media in confronting extremism, and to work on its precise definition and diagnosis of this phenomenon.; By reviewing the opinions of all participants in the confrontation process, including religious scholars, security experts, psychologists, social experts, intellectuals, and intellectuals of society, with the aim of quickly eliminating it (Hawat, 2002, pp. 12-51).

Perhaps it is important to focus on religious scholars, to refute to the recipient all the extremist ideas adopted by terrorists, because the religious, intellectual and cultural confrontation is no less important than the security confrontation, and rather confronting extremist thought with moderate thought precedes all other confrontations.

If the media is able to host strong religious scholars, they will be able to refute terrorists' interpretations of the Qur'anic texts and exploit their wrong interpretations of them in acts of killing, slaughter, and inhuman exploitation of non-Islamic hostages and their torture.

In addition to refuting the wrongful exploitation of interpretations of some Prophetic hadiths, removing them from their moral content and focusing on the verbal meaning, the media should host social scientists and psychologists to dissect the mentality of extremists, with the aim of contributing to preventing others from sympathizing with them.

The positive role played by the media is to study, discuss and analyze emerging phenomena, including the phenomenon of extremism, and refute its claims and

falsehoods, while being careful in presenting the truth and avoiding exaggeration or belittlement. The security authorities must provide the media with information and facts about this phenomenon and any new developments regarding it in a timely manner. In a way that clarifies the true picture and does not leave a void that others exploit poorly (Qirat, 2012, p.78).

At the same time, the positive role of the media requires the presence of media cadres at the event level that are constantly developed through training and by strengthening the religious, national and humanitarian motives. For this, appropriate strategic planning must be available to meet the challenges of the present and the requirements of the future.

We need an enlightened media that deepens moderation with all its noble values, a media that recognizes the other and discusses their issues with freedom and honesty, so that every citizen can trust what he is dealing with. Otherwise, the alternative is ready, which is the hateful media that puts poison in honey and transmits information from a point of view that is not devoid of Sometimes it is a falsification of facts and an embellishment of falsehood (Qirat, 2011, p.75).

The joint Arab media strategy must aim to achieve and maintain national security, and to achieve the following goals:

- 1- Forming public opinion against fanaticism and extremism in its various forms.
- 2- Purifying media programs from everything that might encourage deviation, extremism, and extremism.
- 3- Renewing the language of media discourse, correcting misconceptions of jihad for the sake of God, and distinguishing between terrorism and legitimate resistance against the occupation.
- 4- Highlighting that the Islamic religion calls for upholding the values of tolerance and rejecting terrorism, extremism and violence.
- 5- Work to ensure that media programs strive to present religion in its correct image, and to purify programs from new preachers and their misleading fatwas.
- 6- Supporting the qualification and development of Arab media cadres capable of dealing with the era and its modern technologies, and aware of the goals of its Arab media mission.
- 7- Enlightening Arab public opinion about its family responsibilities, towards protecting emerging generations from falling into the clutches of extremism and raising their cultural awareness.
- 8- Educating the Arab citizen and making him always aware of what is going on around him and what is being plotted against him, and consolidating societal awareness about the dire consequences of the phenomenon of extremism.
- 9- Draining the sources of intellectual deviation, and blocking all its outlets, through targeted and directed media programs.
- 10- Adopting comprehensive media programs aimed at developing general national awareness, consecrating love of the homeland and the importance of belonging to it and confronting the fallacies and tendentious ideas presented through the media to negatively influence youth (Mustafa, p.132).

The researchers believe that the media must address all dimensions of the phenomenon of extremism in jurisprudential, scientific, social, security, cultural

and intellectual ways, and not be satisfied with just one role, as all roles are complementary to each other in the process of confronting extremist thought, and the media must also benefit from modern media technologies in disseminating information with the aim of influencing opinion, Public awareness, guidance, and development of minds and ideas.

In conclusion, the researcher believes that it is necessary to put forward the idea of forming a team of international experts in the field of media to discuss ways of joint media awareness against extremism, to enable the international media to build a broad base of international public opinion that besieges extremism in thought or action, and strengthens efforts aimed at eliminating it.

Conclusion:

The media is a trust and a responsibility, and the media institution is like the educational institution in terms of its impact on shaping the structure of societies and shaping their features. The impact of the media institution may outweigh the educational one, which necessitates investing the media in directing our youth towards what will bring good and benefit to our society in the long term, and in the conclusion of this research paper. The researcher recommends some recommendations that she hopes will be implemented:

- 1- The media should work to place a culture of development and unity on its agenda instead of a culture of hatred, violence, and extremism.
- 2- Stopping media campaigns based on incitement and fabrication of lies, which would deepen the culture of sectarian violence and self-love in Arab society.
- 3- Eliminating terrorism and extremism requires unity and national will, regardless of political differences, just as it requires preserving dignity and human rights.
- 4- Eliminating extremism requires putting an end to sectarian discrimination.
- 5- Adopting an integrated scientific, political, economic, social, cultural, educational and religious strategy and involving civil society in it, which begins with prevention, passes through protection, and reaches care by taking long and medium-term measures, and at the same time necessary immediate measures within an institutional framework, in addition to the security and intelligence aspects, which will be its basic foundation. A comprehensive political will and general national consensus to dry up the sources of terrorism economically and financially, and work to reduce the levels of unemployment, poverty and marginalization, as well as a community media, cultural and educational plan to spread the culture of non-violence, tolerance, recognition of the other, acknowledgment of pluralism, coexistence and equal citizenship, and addressing the problems and laws of uprooting and exclusion that have had negative effects on Society and national unity, and such a matter requires concrete and serious steps to achieve true national, political and societal reconciliation within a legal and legal framework.

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